

Spectrophotometric Study of Metal Complexes with Dimethyl Purpurogallin

Yag Dutt, D. P. Goel and R. P. Singh

A spectrophotometric study of colour reactions of zirconium, thorium, molybdenum (VI) and iron (III) has been carried out. It is observed that molybdenum (VI) forms a 1 : 1 complex, zirconium and thorium, 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes and iron (III), 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 complexes with the above ligand.

Purpurogallin, the well known synthetic dye, has been used for the gravimetric determination¹ of thorium, cerium, zirconium, molybdenum, lead and a number of other metals and for spectrophotometric determination of zirconium² and germanium³. Purpurogallin has more than one active chelating centre and forms complexes of indefinite stoichiometry with most of the metal ions. It is also not very selective for the above reasons. Dimethyl purpurogallin has only one chelating centre⁴ and is, therefore, expected to form complexes of definite composition and also be more selective than purpurogallin. The only reported work with dimethyl-purpurogallin has been the determination of stability constants of bivalent metal complexes with this ligand⁴.

Dimethyl-purpurogallin gives colour reactions with a number of metal ions. In the present communication, studies on complexes of dimethyl-purpurogallin with zirconium (IV), molybdenum (VI), thorium (IV) and iron (III) have been reported.

EXPERIMENTAL

Dimethyl-purpurogallin was prepared by the method of Haworth *et al.*⁵ and was purified by crystallization from ethanol. A solution of dimethyl-purpurogallin (DMP) in ethanol was used for all the studies. Solutions of the metal ions were prepared from reagent grade samples of the corresponding salts and were standardized gravimetrically.

A Unicam SP 600 spectrophotometer was used for most of the studies and a Metrohm pH meter, model E-350 was employed for pH measurement.

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Spectrophotometric Study of zirconium (IV)—DMP complex: Absorption spectra of the reagent and zirconium-reagent complex were taken at different concentrations of hydrochloric acid. The reagent has maximum absorbance at 410 nm and the position of absorption maximum remains unchanged by varying acidity. The zirconium complex has maximum absorbance at 400 and 470 nm. The absorbance of the system is practically constant in the range 0.2–1 *N* hydrochloric acid concentration and decreases at higher acidities. However, the position of the absorption maxima of the zirconium complexes remain unchanged by increasing acidity. The effect of increasing reagent concentration shows that O.D. increases with increasing reagent concentration and is practically constant after 10 fold excess of the reagent has been added. The increasing reagent concentration does not change the absorption maxima of the zirconium complexes.

Job's method of continuous variations was used at various acidities and wavelengths to find out the composition of the complex. In 0.4*N* hydrochloric acid medium, the composition of the complex at 400 and 470 nm, the absorption maxima of the complex, was found to be 1 : 2, but by using the wavelength 500 nm, the composition of the complex was found to be 1 : 1 (Fig. 1). Similar results were obtained in 0.8*N* hydrochloric acid medium. This

Fig. 1. Composition of zirconium-DMP complex using Job's method. (Total molarity = $4 \times 10^{-4} M$; 0.4 *N* HCl medium.

shows the formation of two zirconium complexes in the system, the 1 : 1 complex absorbing much less at wavelengths 400 and 470 nm and absorbing to an equal extent at 500 nm than 1 : 2 complex.

Thorium Complexes: Absorption spectra of solutions containing thorium and reagent in the ratio 1 : 8 were taken at various *pH* values. It was found that the absorption maxima of the complex lie at 400 and 460 nm up to *pH* 4.0 and the latter shifts to 470 nm at *pH* 5.5. The optical density of the complex increases with increasing *pH* values up to *pH* 4.0, after which it slowly decreases. All the subsequent readings were, therefore, taken at *pH* 4.0.

Optical density of the complex increases steadily with increasing reagent concentration up to about 4 moles of the reagent, after which it practically remains constant.

Job's method of continuous variations as modified by Vosburgh and Cooper, was used to find out the composition of the complexes formed (Fig. 2). At pH 4.0 using 400 and 460 nm,

Fig. 2. Composition of the thorium complex using Job's method. (Total molarity = $4 \times 10^{-4}M$; pH 4.0).

the wavelengths of the absorption maxima, the composition of the complex was found to be 1 : 2; however, at 520 nm, the maximum in the Job's curve was obtained at metal : ligand ratio 1 : 1. This shows the formation of two thorium complexes (1 : 1 and 1 : 2) in thorium-DMP system, the 1 : 1 complex being less significant and absorbing much less than 1 : 2 complex at pH 4.0.

Molybdenum (VI)—Complex: Absorption spectra of solutions containing molybdate and reagent in the ratio 1 : 4 were taken at different pH values. Maximum absorption due to the complex takes place at 400 and 460 nm. The complex has practically the same absorbance in the pH range 2.0–4.0 and it decreases at higher pH values. All the subsequent studies were carried out at pH 2.5.

Job's method of continuous variations was used to find out the composition of the complex at different wavelengths using equimolar and non-equimolar solutions (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Composition of molybdenum-DPM complex by Job's method (Total molarity = $2.4 \times 10^{-4}M$; pH 2.5).

It was observed that the composition of the complex is 1 : 1 at all wavelengths showing the formation of only one complex under these conditions.

The decrease in optical density of the complex with increasing pH values above pH 4.0, shows that the molybdenum (VI)—DMP complex dissociates at higher pH values and more of the complex gets formed only in the acidic medium, where molybdenum exists as MoO_2^{++} ions. The structure of the complex may, therefore, be written as below.

Iron (III) complexes : Absorption spectra of solutions containing iron (III) and reagent in the ratio 1 : 10 were taken at different pH values. Maximum absorption due to the complexes takes place at 470 and 550 nm at lower pH values and it gradually shifts to 465 and 510 nm at higher pH values (Fig. 4). The optical density due to the complex is constant in the pH -range 5.5–8.0.

Fig. 4. Absorption spectrum of ferric complex with dimethylpurpurugallin at various pH values [$Fe(III)$ = $4 \times 10^{-5} M$; $RH = 4 \times 10^{-4} M$].

Job's method of continuous variations was used to find the composition of complexes formed at different pH values. The composition was found to be 1 : 2 at pH 3.0 and 1 : 3

Fig. 5. Composition of ferric complex with dimethyl purpurogallin using Job's method. (Total molarity = $4 \times 10^{-4}M$).

at pH 8.0 at all wavelengths (Fig. 5).

Department of Chemistry,
University of Delhi,
Delhi-7.

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